

MANUFACTURING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CONTINUOUS RECYCLED CARBON FIBER UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

High-performance composites are integral to aerospace, automotive, and renewable energy sectors, but their reliance on virgin carbon fibres poses significant environmental and economic sustainability challenges globally. While recycled carbon fibres (rCF) offer a more environmentally friendly solution, their discontinuous nature significantly limits their mechanical performance, restricting their application in high-performance recycled carbon fibre-reinforced polymers (rCFRP). This study addresses this critical limitation by introducing and fully characterizing a novel continuous rCF material that retains fibre continuity, enabling superior mechanical performance and broadening the range of applications for rCF in demanding engineering contexts.

This research fills a significant knowledge gap by being the first to comprehensively characterize the mechanical properties of rCFRP manufactured with continuous rCF reclaimed from end-of-life carbon/epoxy Type III pressure vessels. The continuous rCF was produced using a thermal recycling technology, which stripped the polymer matrix, allowing the rCF to be unwound and tow length to be retained. Unidirectional (UD) panels were fabricated using a custom filament winding process optimized to achieve high fibre alignment, fibre volume fractions, and uniform resin distribution.

Mechanical testing of the panels, including tensile (ASTM D3039), compression (ASTM D6641), flexural (ASTM D7264), and short-beam shear testing (ASTM D2344), revealed that the mechanical properties of continuous rCFRP match or exceed those of industrial-grade virgin carbon fibre composites. Comparative analysis with virgin fibres (T700S-50C-12K and T300-50B-6K) showed that continuous rCF composites achieve performance metrics positioned between high-strength T700 and industrial-grade T300 composites. These results demonstrate that the retention of fibre length and alignment in continuous rCF directly addresses the performance limitations associated with conventional discontinuous rCF.

By demonstrating that continuous rCF can achieve performance comparable to standard virgin carbon fibre composites, this study establishes a critical pathway for integrating recycled fibres into high-performance applications. The enhanced directional properties, comparable fibre volume fractions, and

compatibility with existing manufacturing processes make continuous rCF a transformative material for sustainable engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

The global demand for carbon fibre (CF) was estimated at 115 kilotonnes (kt) in 2023 and is projected to more than double to 280 kt by 2030 [1]. This growth is driven by the widespread use of carbon fibre-reinforced polymers (CFRPs) across sectors committed to decarbonisation, particularly transportation, renewable energy, and hydrogen storage. In the wind energy sector, CFRPs are increasingly used in multi-megawatt turbine blades due to their exceptional stiffness-to-weight ratio. As a result, wind energy is expected to surpass aerospace as the leading consumer of carbon fibre, with estimated demand reaching 20 kt for wind turbine blades alone [1][2].

Similarly, in the hydrogen economy, CFRPs are critical for constructing lightweight, high-pressure storage vessels. These composites improve safety and transport efficiency while reducing system weight. Currently, the pressure vessel segment accounts for approximately 12% of global CF demand and is poised for significant expansion alongside the hydrogen sector [1][3][4].

Despite its performance benefits, carbon fibre production is highly energy-intensive, contributing up to 50% of the total carbon footprint of offshore wind turbine blades [5]. Globally, CF manufacturing results in over 4 million tonnes of CO₂-equivalent emissions each year [6]. At the end of their service life, CFRP components present substantial recycling challenges. Most recycled carbon fibre (rCF) is recovered in chopped or discontinuous forms, which compromises fibre alignment and mechanical performance. Consequently, applications for rCF remain limited to non-structural or low-performance uses, reducing its commercial value and its ability to offset virgin CF consumption.

A key step toward a circular composite economy is the development of recycling technologies capable of retaining fibre continuity. Continuous rCF has the potential to deliver mechanical performance comparable to virgin fibre composites, enabling structural applications and reducing the environmental impact of CFRP systems. This study investigates such a solution focusing on the manufacturing and mechanical characterisation of unidirectional (UD) composites made from continuous recycled carbon fibre.

The reclaimed fibres in this study originate from end-of-life Type III carbon/epoxy pressure vessels and are recovered using a thermal process that preserves fibre length. Through a custom filament winding process, these fibres are reconstituted into continuous UD laminates and benchmarked against virgin fibre panels. The goal is to demonstrate that continuous rCF can close the performance gap that has historically limited recycled composites, and thereby support scalable, high-value reuse of CFRPs in demanding structural applications.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Panel fabrication was performed using a flat mandrel system designed to simulate industrial-grade unidirectional layups. To ensure repeatability, each batch used identical processing conditions, and samples were drawn from the same tool. Environmental controls during resin infusion (ambient humidity and temperature ~22°C) were maintained to limit variability. Post-processing included oven curing and standardised trimming to generate test coupons according to ASTM specifications.

Recycled carbon fibre was recovered from end-of-life Type III carbon/epoxy pressure vessels using a thermal recycling process. This method effectively removes the matrix while retaining the fibre tow length and orientation. The reclaimed fibres were processed into continuous tows suitable for filament winding. Two virgin fibre grades (T700 and T300) were used as benchmarks. An epoxy system, Araldite LY556 with Aradur 917 hardener and accelerator DY070—was used for both reclaimed and virgin fibre panels.

3 MANUFACTURING PROCESS

The filament winding process (Figure 1) was executed on a modified flat-panel mandrel to enable consistent unidirectional (UD) layering. The process required precise environmental control, as the resin system's viscosity and curing profile are highly temperature-dependent. The resin bath was equipped with an immersion heater and maintained between 50–60°C to ensure optimal flow and wet-out characteristics. A tensioning system ensured even fibre delivery, while programmable creel rotation and mandrel speed facilitated the accurate layering of fibres. To improve panel quality, wide flash tape and square rubber rope were used around mandrel edges to minimize resin leakage and edge defects. The introduction of a reinforced PTFE film as a release layer helped mitigate warpage and surface irregularities caused by mandrel thermal expansion. Banding trials were crucial to establish the correct number of layers and minimize tow overlap, which could lead to increased void content or fibre misalignment. Vacuum bagging followed immediately after winding, ensuring thorough compaction and air evacuation during curing. The wrapped mandrel was cured in a Carbolite Gero oven with thermocouples for thermal tracking.

Figure 1: Filament Winding Schematic

Flat panel filament winding was used to manufacture unidirectional (UD) composite panels. The winding mandrel was treated with Frekote 700NC release agent and lined with Tooltec CS5 PTFE film. Bandwidth trials ensured consistent tow coverage and panel thickness. The resin bath was preheated to 50°C with nip pressure set to 0.5 bar and fibre tension at 10 N/tow. During winding, defects such as tow fluff, splicing, char deposits, and entanglement were observed (Figure 3). Excess resin was allowed to drip off before caul plates were bolted on, and vacuum bagging was performed before curing in a Carbolite Gero oven.

4 MECHANICAL TESTING

The mechanical testing program adhered to internationally recognized ASTM standards and focused on characterizing different failure modes and load responses. Test listed in Figure 2 were performed to characterise the vCF and rCF UD Panels. Tensile testing utilized dogbone specimens with hydraulic wedge grips to avoid slippage, and extensometers were mounted to measure axial strain directly. Compression tests used anti-buckling fixtures to stabilize the specimen and ensure valid compressive failure modes. Flexural tests were performed in three-point bending mode, with supports modified to account for composite anisotropy and prevent stress concentration at the loading nose. Short beam shear (SBS) testing was used to assess interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), providing insight into fibre-matrix adhesion and resin distribution. Each test was performed on a minimum of five specimens to ensure statistical validity. X-ray computed tomography (XCT) scans were conducted pre- and post-test to

investigate internal failure mechanisms such as delamination, fibre pull-out, and void evolution. Test data were plotted as stress-strain curves and benchmarked against the performance of virgin CFRP panels under identical conditions.

Mechanical characterisation followed ASTM standards: tensile testing (ASTM D3039), compression (ASTM D6641), flexural (ASTM D7264), and short beam shear (ASTM D2344). Non-destructive testing was performed using X-ray CT scanning to examine internal defects, fibre distribution, and porosity. Key test parameters included dogbone specimens for tensile tests and torque-controlled gripping to prevent slippage or misalignment.

Figure 2: Tests performed on vCF and rCF UD Panels

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the filament winding process of reclaimed carbon fibres, defects such as tow fluff, splicing, char deposits, and entanglement were observed (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Defects observed with reclaimed carbon fibre filament winding process

CT scan analysis revealed consistent internal structures in virgin and recycled panels. The fibre volume fraction (V_f) was highest in T700 panels (64.7%), followed by T300 (60.8%), and reclaimed rCF panels (46.3%). Mechanical properties of continuous rCF panels showed intermediate performance, positioned between T700 and T300, proving their capability for high-performance applications. Despite the challenges with wet winding heads, towpreg-based manufacturing improved consistency and reduced defect incidence. Fluff formation and tow breakage were the primary causes of irregularity. Panels demonstrated sufficient integrity for structural applications with good matrix-fibre interaction and fibre alignment.

The tensile properties of continuous rCF composites were found to be within 10–15% of T300 virgin panels, indicating a significant improvement over conventional discontinuous rCF. Compression strength also showed promising results, with the rCF panels demonstrating good fibre alignment and minimal buckling artifacts. The flexural modulus and strength values confirmed the stiffness and energy absorption potential of the material. Short beam shear tests revealed that while interfacial strength was slightly lower in rCF composites, the values remained within acceptable engineering margins. XCT analysis of cured panels indicated low porosity levels (~3–5%), especially in panels fabricated using the towpreg head. Defect mapping through XCT visualisation showed uniform fibre distribution and fewer voids in virgin panels, but reclaimed fibre panels exhibited consistent morphology post-winding. Failure surface examination revealed fibre pull-out and matrix cracking in rCF panels, whereas virgin panels showed more brittle failure. Overall, the mechanical performance supports the suitability of continuous rCF for structural applications, particularly in cost-sensitive sectors seeking sustainability.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that continuous recycled carbon fibre composites manufactured through filament winding can achieve mechanical properties comparable to commercial virgin fibre composites. Optimisation of winding parameters and defect control is essential to ensure quality. The results validate continuous rCF as a viable and sustainable alternative for high-performance composites, enabling integration into critical sectors such as aerospace and automotive manufacturing. Future work will focus on further automation, improved quality control, and performance under environmental ageing and fatigue loading.

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